

FORMATION OF CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS IN STUDENTS AS A SOCIAL-PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract: in this article, it is considered that the development of critical thinking in students is an important pedagogical problem. factors, methods, directions of development of critical thinking are shown. it is proposed to use the activity of national heroes as a didactic tool for the development of critical thinking in students.

Key words: student, critical thinking, activities of national heroes, pedagogical factors, communication, cooperation.

Introduction. Today's educational processes require the use of pedagogical approaches that incorporate new concepts and models of organizational learning. The educational process organized based on new approaches should first of all be directed to the personal-intellectual, moral and cultural development of students. Based on this, the necessity of enrichment with pedagogical technologies and mechanisms that serve to form critical thinking skills in the subjects of the continuous education and training process is increasing. In Jakhan education, priority is given to educating each individual to independent, logical and critical thinking. Because the ability to think, especially critical thinking, is the greatest wealth of a person. The goal of education is the formation of critical thinking in students, which is considered an intuitive and individual pedagogical phenomenon.

Scientific analysis of the problem. In today's strategized, globalized educational processes, the development of critical thinking competencies in students in order to form their moral image, worldview, healthy beliefs, their own point of view and position is manifested as an important pedagogical necessity. . Studying the activities of the heroes of the Uzbek people and guiding them to learn from them is one of the important educational tools, so that students can analyze their own and others' activities and actions based on critical thinking.

In the heritage of our ancestors, admonitions and appeals to young people have a special place. For this purpose, they wrote poems, pandnoms, appeals in the genre of advice. Folk epics express people's dreams about an ideal person who understands his identity, has his own position, and thinks critically. It

should be emphasized that epic heroes such as Gorogli, Alpomish, Avazkhan, Ashiq Gharib and Shokhsanam, Vomik and Uzro, Farhad and Shirin, as well as Tomaris, Shiroq, Najmiddin Kubro, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, In the example of the activities of our national heroes such as Temur Malik, Pahlavon Mahmud, Amir Temur, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, students have special pedagogical opportunities to form their own points of view, express their views and attitudes, and develop critical thinking skills. National heroes can be the greatest value and example school for the young generation.

Our thinking ancestors always held high the honor and value of human beings and stressed the need to show respect to every person, regardless of language, religion, nationality, and social status in society. They are those who believe that punishment for crime and incentive for virtue are inevitable. Calling to do good deeds, to control one's ego, not to give free rein to anger and rage, not to spoil the light of humanity with corruption and pleasure, and that the most beautiful dress for a person is knowledge, manners, morality, who emphasized the need to be harmonious in relationships. Eastern thinkers believed that parents and teachers should recognize the child's identity, approach it as a value, and treat it with respect.

Critical thinking expresses the levels of intellectual development and activity of a person. The issues of intellectual education and thinking development have been recognized as actual pedagogical processes in every era. Scholars and scholars of each era have shown their own views, methods and directions in this regard. The issues of mental education were studied and researched by Greek philosophers and Eastern thinkers as a leading scientific direction.

In many higher and scientific research institutes of the world, a number of scientific studies and projects aimed at developing critical thinking in subjects of the educational process are being implemented. The well-known American scientist William Graham Sumner considered the importance of critical thinking in personal life and educational activities extremely important and conducted research on the problems of forming critical thinking in a person. Sumner argues that critical thinking is essential to a healthy and productive society. According to the expert, a person should strive to make the right decisions, analyze and evaluate objectively.

Edward M. Glaser's scientific research states: "Critical thinking is the rational, unbiased analysis and evaluation of available facts, observations, and evidence."

Students' critical thinking process is carried out step by step. That's why the questions presented to the students in the classes regarding specific problems, historical events, and real events become more complex than simple. While students are relatively less active in simple questions, in complex questions they turn more deeply to psychological processes such as self-concentration, memory recovery, and use of their creative abilities.

The main factor of protecting young people from various "mass culture" attacks is to express their reaction to the happenings, to analyze, to develop critical thinking. To form a conscious attitude towards the life of society in students and young people, to strengthen the sense of belonging to the happening events, to be intolerant towards the forces attacking our national culture, peace of mind, own point of view, and a sense of national pride. Having it is of particular importance.

Critical thinking can be interpreted in pedagogy as a term that defines the level of intellectual development of a person. Because the process of critical thinking is manifested as a product of a person's acquired knowledge, intellectual ability, and culture. Critical thinking includes a number of psychological and pedagogical processes. Psychological processes such as perception, intellect, memory, intuition, emotion, intuition form the objective structure of critical thinking. It should be emphasized that critical thinking is based on accurate information, knowledge, and experience.

The existence of pedagogical concepts such as culture, spirituality, morality, worldview, intellectual development are the subjective foundations of critical thinking. The educational process, organized on the basis of the principles of development of critical thinking, motivates students towards the goal and forms social activity in them.

Conclusion. It is also important to form the competence of expressing one's opinion, attitude, and views in students who can think critically. Critical thinking allows students to raise their knowledge to a new level, as well as to synthesize and generalize their existing knowledge, understanding, and information with new information. In this, the processes of reflection, imitation, expression of one's immanence and point of view, communication with the team, and discussion are activated.

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